

CYBERLENINKA

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OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Murodullayeva Dilbar Muxammadiyevna

TALABA YOSHLARNING TAFAKKUR VA DUNYOQARASHINI

RIVOJLANISHIDA INTELLEKT VA KREATIVLIKNING O'RNI

DRJI

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WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

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